

**ABOUT THE DEVELOPMENT AND RULES OF THE FOOTBALL GAME
О ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИИ И ПРАВИЛАХ ФУТБОЛЬНОГО МАТЧА**

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Annotation. This article gives some information about the history of ancient Football, its origin, stages of development. The rules of the game as well as the current game of football, what new rules have been introduced and changes have been considered.

Keywords: match rule, referee, whistle, controversial ball, FIFA, OFK, UEFA.

Аннотация. В этой статье представлен ряд сведений об истории Древнего футбола, его происхождении, этапах развития. Были рассмотрены правила игры, а также футбольная игра в настоящее время, какие новые правила были введены и какие изменения произошли.

Ключевые слова: Правило игры, судья, свисток, спорный мяч, ФИФА, АФК, УЕФА.

In order to create an effective system of selection and training of promising and talented players, to form a quality sports reserve for national teams and professional football clubs, to train, retrain and train football coaches and referees on the basis of international requirements and standards, as well as in accordance with the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 5, 2018:

The Ministry of physical education and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan, the Football Association of Uzbekistan and OJSC Uzbekneftgaz: "Bunyodkor" stadium, together with the complex of all buildings and facilities (next referred to as “Bunyodkor” stadium), is the main base of the Football Association of Uzbekistan for the organization of the training and training process for the National Football teams and the conduct of sports competitions and other events; children's and youth football academies in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent, which carry out their selection (selection) work in order to prepare promising young players in a professional way later and create a quality sports reserve for National Football teams and professional football clubs in football, as well as the organization of the Republican children's and youth football academy under¹¹³

¹¹³ <https://lex.uz/docs/-3589863?ONDATE=07.04.2022>

Football is one of the oldest games. The English claim that foot ball was very popular in the British Isles as early as the 9th century.

On 26 October 1863, during the formation of the English Football Union in London, the first official rules for this game, consisting of 13 articles, were approved. These rules later became the basis of the game of football for all other national associations. In the early rules of the game of football, it is determined that the length of the field should not exceed 200 yards (183 meters), the width should not exceed 100 yards (91 meters).

The gates were made up of two pillars with no girders between them, and the distance between the pillars was 8 yards (7.32 m). In 1866, a rope was pulled between the posts to limit the height. Another 10 years later, this rope was replaced by a wooden fence.

The goalkeeper had no right to play with the hand. In 1871 it was allowed to play right-handed, even if only within the goal area. It would take more than 30 years for a goalkeeper to gain the right to play by hand even within the penalty area (1902).

For a long time, there was neither a penalty Ball nor an 11-meter shot. The violation was limited to free throws. Finally, one of the strictest penalties of 1891 – an 11-metre shot – was introduced, which is colloquially referred to as a "penalty" in English.

During periods when football was taking shape, team captains kept track of the observance of the rules of the game. On the football field, the referee appeared in 1880, and after 1 year the referee began to take the field with two assistants. The whistle was introduced in 1878, prior to which the referee would use either The Voice or hand movements to stop or restart the game. In those years, the rules were not uniform or binding on all National Football Associations.

Each union could make various changes to these rules at its discretion. This situation created difficulties in holding international meetings or organizing international competitions.

In 1882, the ball was the site of a merger of the Independent Football alliances of England, Scotland, Wales and Ireland. In this, uniform rules were adopted, and an International Council was approved, which had the right to make one or another change in the rules of football.

In 1871, the direction of the Country Cup was confirmed in England. This cup is currently contested by English football teams - the first football match at international level between teams from England and Scotland took place in 1873. When the number of players exceeded 11, their placement on the team was more than it is now. The England team had 7 players on offense, 1 at halfback, as well as 2 defenders and 1 goalkeeper. The Scotland squad had 6 forwards, 2 midfielders.

In the 80s of the XIX century, the game of football began to spread to countries on the European continent. In 1875, football entered the Netherlands and later Denmark. From 1882 he began playing football in Switzerland, from 1890 in the Czech Republic, and from 1897 in Russia.

In 1882, the Directorate of international associations was founded. Finally, on 21 May 1904, an International Football Association, FIFA, was founded, which is now a member of more than 200 nations, following the initiative of France. In addition to FIFA, the European Football Union – UEFA operates from 1954.

Since 1930, the football World Cup has been held every 4 years, and since 1958 the European Championships, in which national teams participate. Football became an Olympic sport in 1900, but officially it was included in the program of the Olympic Games in 1908.

The Asian Football Confederation (AFC) was formed in 1954 and currently brings together about 44 countries

The IFAB (Council of International Football Associations) had made a number of changes to the rules of football at its meeting in Aberdeen in early March. It is envisaged that the changes will be valid from June 1 of this year. So, all competitions that begin are held under a new rule. We bring to your attention information about notable changes.

LIVE WALL. When a penalty shot is set, if the defending side is formed to form a live wall of three players or more, the opponent will not be able to add their players to the live wall to interfere with them. Attackers should be at least a meter from the live wall and not interfere with it. This change is being introduced in order to avoid various conflicts and consequent interruptions when a penalty kick is executed.

GOLNINISHONIZATION. If the player who scored a goal violates the rule when celebrating it (e.g., taking off the jersey), he is later penalized with a yellow card even if that goal is not counted.

The ball into the game KIRITISH. To ' when P is introduced into the game with a free kick in front of the goal, he does not have to leave the penalty area. Now the defender can receive the ball inside the penalty area and start the attack. In turn, opposing forwards will not enter the penalty area at this point, until the ball is picked up by the defender. It is said that this makes pressing difficult and can lead to an increase in the tempo of the game. Because, fearing the opponent's pressing, there were cases of kicking the ball far away, the defenders would now have more chances of launching their team's attack from the ground.

HAND PLAY. Now in any alfoz, a goal is not counted if the ball hits the hand and is scored on the opponent's goal. It is no longer distinguished in such cases as a deliberate or unintentional hand touch. When determining such situations, VAR's role is expected to be very large.

PLAYER SWAP.The player being replaced will now leave the field from the side line that is close to him. It is located in the reserve seat and the new player will not have to leave the field from the point of descent. Naturally, this is being assessed as a struggle for situations of stretching the playing time.

Penalty.It is enough for goalkeepers to stand on the goal line with only one foot while a penalty is being kicked from the new season. Previously, it was required that both legs not protrude forward.The reason for such changes was that in so many situations the judges ignored violations of this style of rule.

CONTROVERSIAL BALL.Football will no longer have this concept. The umpires will not roll the two sides and discard the disputed ball.Instead, the side that owns the ball will continue to play until the whistle rings. If necessary, they can give the ball to the opponent. The exception is mabodo, where a match is stopped at the penalty area, the kick-off is made by the goalkeeper.

A CARD TO THE COACH.From the new season, referees will be able to show cards not only to players on the field, but also to the coach or other officials.As it was, the umpires had the option to exclude the coaches from the game, but since the card was not shown, there were often misunderstandings for the spectators.

VAR.As of the 2019/2020 football season, the VAR system will now also begin to operate in the English Premier League, and thus this system will be in effect in all of the strong five championships. Recall that in Italy and Germany from the 2017/18 season, and in Spain and France from the 2018/19 season, reference to video cameras was introduced. Also in 2018, the VAR system was used at the World Cup in Russia as well as the last European Champions League, starting with the nimchorak final.This system will assist the chief referee in the decisions of the referee in terms of video cameras, mainly in 4 different situations – scoring, penalty, red cards and determining the player. At the same time, the final decision will still remain with the chief referee on the field.

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